

TITLE

Clusterization and Mapping of Waste Recycling Science. Evolution of Research From 2002 to 2012

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ABSTRACT

Characterization of waste recycling (WR) research has to start by defining the scope of this scientific area. Previous works and expert assessment recommend the adoption of an inclusive definition, approved by the European Environmental Agency, with the aim of including all relevant uses of waste within this study. An ad-hoc designed “capture” strategy has been used to retrieve WR-related peer-reviewed journal papers from selected databases, and the information contained in their author keyword field has been thoroughly cleaned by means of text mining tools. Author keyword co-occurrence data has been used for building a similarity measure between keywords, plus cluster analysis for revealing the main WR research issues being addressed by the scientific community. Results of cluster analysis have been further analyzed using [network-analysis-advanced visualization tools](#) to determine which clusters formed strongly-linked research areas that could set the main cognitive divisions of WR science. This process has been repeated with 2002 and 2012 data, and science maps reflecting main research areas and clusters have been generated, to enable researchers to detect changes in WR during this interval. Results show that WR, as defined in this study, mainly deals with the recovery of basic, widely used raw materials like water and fertile soil. Energy generation [and waste management](#) ~~is are another other~~ relevant fields that shows an interesting evolution from 2002, showing signs of growth in research, together with the emergence of sub-areas reflecting consolidating research specialties. Future research lines [based on variations detected in the science maps](#) are posed ~~based on other variations detected in the science maps~~.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. FIELD DEFINITION

To the layman, waste recycling (WR) is a clearly defined and neatly divided field, as neat as the container system where citizens are often urged to classify their daily residues. However, when trying to characterize research around WR, the first issue a researcher must deal with is the definition of a field like this, consisting of a wide range of materials to be treated and a full variety of techniques to be employed.

[Depending on the source](#) ~~T~~this field is defined in many different ways, ~~depending on the source~~. Some of the definitions explicitly exclude thermal combustion of waste from WR (US EPA, 2012), while others adopt a wider scope considering the recovery of waste as a valuable input for other processes, whether in its original or transformed state. Several specialized terminology services were browsed through for available definitions, and the following proposal from the European Environmental Agency was chosen:

“A method of recovering waste as resources which includes the collection, and often involving the treatment, of waste products for use as a replacement of all or part of the raw material in a manufacturing process.” (European Environment Agency, 2012)

Some important facts of this definition lie within its inclusiveness: broad terms like “raw material” and “manufacturing process” considerably expand the WR field to limits further than the “glass, paper and organics” concept that the average citizen imagines. In addition to this, collection and separation work form part of WR, these being steps of the utmost importance in the recovery of many types of waste (Demirbas, 2011). Previous bibliometric works in this field have ~~pointed-out~~ indicated the high interdisciplinarity of this field, together with the increasing importance of energy issues in research concerning WR (Garechana, Río-Belver, Cilleruelo, & Gavilanes-Trapote, 2012b), so the wide-broad scope of this definition seems to be accurate for the research presented in this paper. Additional explanations about the choice of this definition can be found at (Garechana, Río-Belver, Cilleruelo, & Gavilanes-Trapote, 2012a).

1.2. ABOUT SCIENCE CHARACTERIZATION AND MAPPING

A frequent parallelism in literature relates science characterization studies with the cartographic mapping of a particular geographic area, since both aim at guiding a decision makers by providing them giving him with qualitative and quantitative information about his- their surroundings. Government R&D policy makers, large research laboratories and universities, among others, are some of the actors that show concern about identifying the main researchers, affiliations and concepts that play a relevant role in their scientific specialties, and their evolution. Expert assessment, coming either from in-house company staff of the firm itself or external experts, is a recurrent and essential resource to include in science characterization attempts, but however, there is an overall consensus pointing at the need of quantitatively reinforcing the judgment of experts. Human judgment is quite subjective, and no scientist can be an expert in a wide range of scientific specialties. In addition to this, it is difficult for a researcher examining the domain from a particular discipline to have an adequate understanding of the whole (Boyack, Klavans, & Börner, 2005).

Scientometrics is the quantitative study of scientific communication, which applies bibliometrics, among other techniques, to scientific literature (Börner, Chen, & Boyack, 2003). Databases that keep track of scholarly communications are a great source of information for quantitative studies in science characterization, since given that -scientific literature is assumed to represent scientific activity insofar as -, in the extent that a great deal of scientific activity is published in journal articles, proceedings and other communications. There are many types of analysis that can be conducted using the bibliometric information contained in scientific databases. Among all the publication types available in there, peer reviewed journal articles guarantee the quality of the indexed publications via a peer review process, and usually have a great deal of well-structured indexing information, perfectly suitable for text mining analysis (Porter & Cunningham, 2005).

It is in tThe conjunction of scientometrics and visualization techniques is from where science mapping comes from. Maps of science are two or three dimensional representations of a scientific field, where the items on the map refer to themes in the mapped field. In these maps the items are positioned in such a way that those topics that are closely related to each other

are positioned in proximity to each other's vicinity, and whereas -unrelated topics are distant from each other (Noyons, 2001). Two key variables in science mapping are the unit of analysis and the similarity measure to be used (Börner et al., 2003), the former will be the item reflected in the map while the latter will be used to determine the degree of proximity between the items.

Depending on the questions that the map of science comes to address, there will be some items more suitable than others to characterize the field. For example, a map based on co-occurrence of authors is more likely to unravel a social structure of a scientific field, while a map based on co-occurrences of classification codes rather is more likely to describe the relation between content elements (Noyons, 2005). Maps built using journals, or some classification scheme based on aggregation of journals such as ISI's Subject Categories are used to delineate specialties, reflect hierarchies, levels of application and thematic proximities with different levels of granularity (Bassecoulard & Zitt, 1999). Semantic or co-word maps, on the other hand, reflect words, terms or clusters of words that represent publications containing them such (Noyons, 2005) and are used to understand determine -the cognitive structure of a field (Börner et al., 2003) or to understand the micro structure of a research specialty (Bhattacharya & Basu, 1998). Each of these approaches has its own particular limitations and drawbacks difficulties: Some journals are multidisciplinary or "general", distorting fine-grain analysis (Bassecoulard & Zitt, 1999), whereas the journal aggregates sometimes are overlapping or are inaccurate (Leydesdorff & Rafols, 2009). On the other side hand, co-word maps have to deal with the problems associated with semantic and lexical variations, as detailed discussed -in further later -sections.

Many of the similarity measures are based on citation data. Co-citation, bibliographic coupling or direct citation are well known and widely used measures. The reference (Boyack & Klavans, 2010) makes provides -a good description and evaluates their relative performance. The similarity can also be determined by analyzing data other than citations. The number of times some certain words, authors or items from a classification scheme co-occur together in a set of publications can be used to determine the similarity between those items. The choice of the most suitable similarity measure will again depend on the purpose of the analysis and the availability of the data.

Scientific databases are good information sources for science characterization. Among all the publication types available in these databases, peer reviewed journal articles guarantee the quality of the indexed publications via peer review process, and usually have a great deal of well-structured indexing information, perfectly suitable for text mining analysis (Porter & Cunningham, 2005).

Some information fields in scientific databases are shaped for optimizing the user's information retrieval process, allowing them to easily find related work, or quickly manipulate the results of a query by filtering the retrieved items by topics or areas. This is the case of Web of Science's Subject Categories or SCOPUS Subject Areas, these are cognitive categories where scientific production is indexed, following analytic procedures (Pudovkin & Garfield, 2002) that may vary between databases. Similarly, many journals ask submitting authors to provide a set of keywords which, in opinion of the author, best characterize the contents of the submitted

work. These author keywords, as well as the automatic keywords indexed by some databases (Thomson Reuters, 2013b) can be used to enhance the information retrieval experience of the database user. Additionally, both categorization and keyword indexing provide the researcher with powerful tools to characterize the intellectual fingerprint of a particular scientific field, by first detecting the main keywords/categories present in a dataset and thereafter inferring the relationships between them via citation or co-occurrence analysis (White & McCain, 1997). Further characterization work can be conducted by using visualization techniques to build a map of science, a visual representation of the main scientific concepts behind a particular area, and the relationships between them (Garechana, Río-Belver, Cilleruelo, & Gavilanes Trapote, 2011).

There are many studies that have successfully mapped scientific fields using some of the approaches described in this section There are many studies that have successfully mapped scientific fields both using keywords and cognitive categories, in addition to other items that could be representative of the activity taking place in a particular field (prominent authors, highly cited documents, etc.). A particularly interesting example is the global map of science developed by Leydesdorff and Rafols (2009) that builds a graphical representation of global science by analyzing Web of Science's Subject Categories and the citation links between them. The cancer research mapping done by Cambrosio, Keating, Mercier, Lewison and Mogoutov (2006) is another example of science characterization, achieved by extracting the main keywords present in cancer research by means of text mining tools and then using the number of co-occurrences between keywords to spatially locate each of them, with proximity indicating relationship between concepts. The work of Garechana et al. (2011) and the Places & Spaces website (Börner & Theriault, 2012) may be a good starting point for readers interested in science mapping.

The aim of this paper is to characterize the WR field by identifying the main research areas behind this science, using scientific research published in the most relevant databases as well as in WR specialized databases. Support from experts in the field has been available throughout the whole process thanks to collaboration with IHOBE, the public corporation in charge of supporting the Basque Government's Department for the Environment, Spatial Planning and Agriculture and Fisheries, in the development of its environmental policy (IHOBE, 2012). Cluster analysis is proposed as an exploratory technique, and network analysis is used for subsequent study of the relationships between the discovered clusters, as well as for map generation. This analysis has been performed for the years 2002 and 2012, with the aim of analyzing the evolution taking place that has occurred in WR research.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. DATA SOURCES

Peer-reviewed (PR) journal articles stored in scientific databases are good information sources for tracking scientific activity (Porter & Cunningham, 2005), and this has been the choice made for this study. The text mining software used (Search Technology, 2011) allows information from different databases to be merged and offers proper-suitable tools for cleaning the data and eliminating duplicities. In order to profit-benefit from these advantages, the authors

decided to combine the contents of multiple sources, following the criteria of including those with the widest coverage of PR journals as well as WR specialized sources. Previous works ~~pointed out~~ revealed the importance of social sciences in WR, mainly related with research issuing environmental policies and economics (Garechana et al., 2012b) so the database selection should also take this into account.

A starting point for database selection was the University of Connecticut database locator (University of Connecticut, 2012), for finding environmental sciences specialized data sources. After carefully considering the available options, two databases from WOS were selected, namely the Science Citation Index (SCI) and the Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI). The SCOPUS database was also included due to its wide coverage (Elsevier B.V, 2013), and the EBSCO Green File database was chosen for its specialization in environmental issues, including recycling activities (EBSCO Publishing, 2012).

The extraction of journal articles corresponding to WR science as defined in section **1.1** has been a matter of research by itself. As previously explained, this is a highly multidisciplinary field that remains somehow ill-defined due to the multiple definitions about regarding what should be considered WR; these are probably reasons why some of the most important databases do not offer a “recycling” category in their indexing services. However, INSPEC, an engineering specialized database produced by the Institution of Engineering and Technology does, indexing its recycling related contents in E1840 category, but although it is a relatively small source when compared with the main scientific databases (Thomson Reuters, 2013a) (Elsevier B.V, 2013). The research conducted by Garechana et al. (2012a) provided a method to “capture” WR publications from databases that accept Boolean queries, and their approach was followed in order to download WR journal articles from the selected databases for the years 2002 and 2012, ~~from the selected databases~~. This capture system was further improved by adding some extra exclusion terms (Garechana et al., 2012a) in order to improve its accuracy; this improved system is available upon request to the corresponding author.

The consideration of multiple databases is usually recommendable when tracking scientific activity (Porter & Cunningham, 2005), however, some difficulties were encountered regarding ~~to~~ the indexation information downloaded from each source, given that categorization systems or other automatic indexation services do differ slightly from one to another, making it impossible to merge the contents of those fields. Having discarded some options due to this fact, the authors considered it more advantageous to analyze the information contained in the author keyword field: this field contains the keywords that, in opinion of the author, best characterize the research done, creating a powerful tool with which to characterize the research being undertaken ~~taking place~~. The availability and homogeneity of this field across the three databases in question was another point for ~~its~~ consideration as ~~the~~ pivotal data for the following subsequent steps.

2.2. CLEANING OF KEYWORDS AND SIMILARITY CALCULATION

Textual information contained in the author keyword field is subject to minimum normalization requirements. Some journals ~~tell~~ instruct authors not to provide the plural form of terms or terms that are too general, likewise to avoid the inclusion of acronyms, ~~but~~ however, when data comes from many different journals, as is the case, data cleaning

becomes of the utmost importance. The data cleaning process should take singular and plural forms, acronyms, synonyms, equivalent expressions and corrupted terms with the same meaning as a single word. This is a ~~hard~~difficult, laborious, ~~time-consuming~~ operation considerably eased by the tools of Vantage Point software. A first rough cleaning was conducted using fuzzy matching tools, followed by a fine-grained cleaning stage searching for terms sharing 70% of the letters. Expert assessment was used when ~~ever~~ doubts arose ~~about~~ concerning the meaning of ~~some-certain~~ technical expressions. After the cleaning phase, a list of 10,183 keywords was obtained for ~~the~~ year 2002, versus 21,990 keywords in 2012, with each term occurring in a range from once up to hundreds of times. This being said, it is ~~worth mentioning convenient to point out~~ that the approach taken with the data cleaning phase has been quite conservative, choosing to keep the original form of the word if the grouping criterion was not clear.

In order to delve deeper into these data, relationships between the keywords can be inferred by analyzing the number of co-occurrences between words. Each journal article in this dataset has an average of 5 author keywords. It is ~~therefore~~ reasonable, and fully supported by literature (Rostaing, 1996), to infer a cognitive relationship between each pair of keywords that often co-occur together in this field. The problem ~~in-at~~ this stage lies in the normalization of the raw co-occurrence data, considering ~~the-fact~~ that the more frequently occurring keywords have a ~~higher~~ ~~chance-likelihood~~ of co-occurring many times with the rest of the keywords in the dataset. A good review of several similarity measures often used in bibliometrics can be found in the reference (Klavans & Boyack, 2006), though the accuracy of some of the measures is criticized by Van Eck and Waltman (2009). This paper (Van Eck & Waltman, 2009) makes a review of the more typical similarity measures, concluding that probability based similarity measures do satisfy the desirable mathematical properties. Following this advice, the indirect Salton's Cosine was calculated, also known as the vector-space model (Salton, Wong, & Yang, 1975). This measure should not be confused with other similarity measures with the same name, since this measure takes the full pattern of co-occurrences of each keyword into account, according to the following formula:

$$Cos_{i,j} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N C_{ij} C_{iq}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N C_{ij}^2 \sum_{i=1}^N C_{iq}^2}}$$

Where C_{ij} , C_{iq} are the values adopted by j and q terms in their co-occurrences with the rest of the terms in the dataset.

Co-occurrence matrices were imported into R statistical software, ignoring keywords occurring less than three times within the whole dataset for ~~the~~ year 2012, and less than twice for ~~the~~ year 2002, in order to remove as much noise as possible from the data. Given that these scarcely occurring keywords are the remnants of a thorough cleaning process, the authors considered them perfectly dispensable; in order to improve the subsequent mathematical analysis of relationships between keywords. Salton's Cosine was calculated for the resulting square matrices, producing 1,970 keywords for ~~the~~ year 2002 versus 3,952 keywords for ~~the~~ year 2012.

2.3. CLUSTER ANALYSIS

Many bibliometric analyses have been conducted using clustering techniques to reveal the existing relationships between concepts (words, authors, documents...), leading to the development of many techniques that fall outside the classics studied in statistical textbooks. Examples of this are the simple centers algorithm (Muñoz-Leiva, Viedma-del-Jesús, Sánchez-Fernández, & López-Herrera, 2012; Cobo, López-Herrera, Herrera-Viedma, & Herrera, 2010; Coulter, Monarch, & Konda, 1998), streamer (Kandylas, Upham, & Ungar, 2008) and spectral clustering (Chen, Ibekwe-SanJuan, & Hou, 2010), among others (Callon, Courtial, & Laville, 1991). Classical clustering techniques also have a solid background in bibliometrics, as is the case with hierarchical clustering (Kopcsa & Schiebel, 1998; McCain, 1998; Zong, Shen, Yuan, Hu, Hou, & Deng, 2012; Leydesdorff, 1987) and k-means clustering (Bassecoulard, Lelu, & Zitt, 2007; Janssens, Leta, Glänzel, & De Moor, 2006; Chang, 2012).

R statistical software offers many options to perform cluster analysis in “cluster” package (Maechler, Rousseeuw, Struyf, Hubert, & Hornik, 2012), and hierarchical clustering was executed using the “agnes” command (Rousseeuw & Kaufman, 2005) setting ward’s clusterization method. Hierarchical clustering with using ward’s method has solid precedents in this field (Kopcsa & Schiebel 1998; Zong et al., 2012; Leydesdorff, 1987; Janssens et al., 2006). The most frequent 300 keywords were clustered using this method, to ease the subsequent cluster interpretation process. Reduction of the dataset to the most frequent items is not strange in co-word analysis, given the usually high number of low-occurring keywords of the dataset (An & Wu, 2011; Mohammadi, 2012; Bhattacharya & Basu, 1998). Cluster analysis is known to be quite sensitive to outliers and points that do not add significant information for group discrimination. Removing these observations is something that researchers should consider (Hair, Anderson, Tatham, & Black, 2006) and this has been the case, after careful consideration, with some frequent keywords that had too generalist a meaning, not useful at all for cluster characterization. The words excluded from the analysis are the following: “recycling”, “environmental”, “environment”, “reuse” and “treatment”. Other terms suitable for exclusion were identified, but it was in the aim of the authors to alter the fewest original data as possible.

An often troublesome and quite subjective question in cluster analysis is how to choose the optimum number of clusters to be obtained. After considering options such as the-silhouette calculations (Rousseeuw, 1987) and robustness indices (Hennig, 2008), minimization of average intra-cluster distances (Hair et al., 2006) (ICD) has been the solution adopted in this research. The interest in this technique lies in the detection of several cut-points where ICD is noticeably diminished, to finally achieve a halfway solution between the need for data reduction and the minimization of ICD. [The robustness of the clustering obtained by hierarchical method has been tested calculating the similarity with the clustering proposed by VOSviewer software, using Meila’s VI \(2007\) technique as available in fpc R package \(Hennig, 2013\). VOSviewer is a mapping and clustering software \(Van Eck & Waltman, 2010\) based on an adaptation of Multidimensional Scaling \(MDS\) for spatial positioning of items \(Van Eck, Waltman, Dekker, & Van der Berg, 2010\) and a variant of modularity-based clustering for item grouping \(Waltman, Van Eck, & Noyons, 2010\).](#)

The interpretation of the clusters rested on a basic assumption: the clusterization had grouped the keywords based on their similarity, calculated from the term co-occurrence found in the WR papers downloaded from scientific databases. Each group of closely related keywords should share a common have a research problem they are dealing with in common, and the name of that research problem or scientific specialty should be the identification of each cluster. This step required extensive use of expert assessment, and collaboration with IHOBE (IHOBE, 2012) was of key importance.

CLUSTER MAPPING

The visualization of data is made by generating two maps with VOSviewer software for the years 2002 and 2012, showing the full set of 300 keywords (see figures 1 and 2) colored accordingly with the clusters identified in hierarchical analysis, to give a flavor of the overall distribution of research concepts and their evolution in a decade. Next, the keyword networks have been shrunk in order to getcreate cluster networks, by grouping all keywords in their respective clusters and calculating the resultant cluster-cluster similarity linkages. This has been done by summing adding up the keyword-keyword similarities between clusters. Density plots (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010) of cluster networks for years 2002 and 2012 have been built to getproduce an overview of the general structure of WR science and its evolution (see figures 4 and 5).

Having identified the main clusters in the field, further analysis can be conducted by studying the relationships between them. The network formed by the top 300 keywords and their similarity links was created with network analysis software pajek (Batagelj & Mrvar, 1998), establishing network partitions corresponding to clusters detected in the previous steps. The network was shrunk according to partitions and a cluster network was obtained, the similarity between each pair of clusters being the sum of all keyword-keyword similarities that connect them.

The resulting network was analyzed to determine general research areas in WR that could be formed by two or more clusters. With this purpose in mind, the density based approach used by Batagelj and Mvar (Batagelj & Mrvar, 2001) to identify the main and secondary themes on the news following the 9/11 terrorist attacks has been applied to our data. Maps of science reflecting the structure of clusters and research areas are generated in pajek to give an intuitive overview of the scientific composition of WR science. The research areas identified in this step have been interpreted with the help of experts from IHOBE.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1. INITIAL CHARACTERIZATION

Table 1 summarizes the total amount of PR journal articles retrieved using the modified capture strategy proposed by Garechana et al. (2012a), for years 2002 and 2012. Those articles with an empty author keyword field have been discarded from the dataset.

#INSERT TABLE 1 HERE

The ~~resulting~~ overlap between databases ~~turns out to be~~ is high, at least for PR journal articles. Considering that each article in a database is unique (internal duplicities have been removed from each database before merging), roughly 92% of items could have been captured by exploiting only the database with widest coverage (SCOPUS in this case). This somehow indicates that further works based on PR journal articles would offer little benefit from combining these databases.

The main concepts dominating the WR field can be detected by looking at the top 10 keywords present in each year under study (table 2). Numbers in brackets indicate the proportion of articles in the dataset that have this particular keyword in their author keyword field. It is ~~interesting~~ ~~convenient~~ to point it out that each article in the dataset has an average of 5 author keywords indexed, so percentages shown in table 2 do not exclude each other.

#INSERT TABLE 2 HERE

Given the adopted definition of WR (see section 1.1) it is not surprising to find wastewater and wastewater-related residues in the dataset, this being probably one of the most consumed (and wasted) raw materials in the world. Soil amendment practices, together with energy generation related terms, occupy the main positions for both years. The following keyword maps ~~come to~~ illustrate this fact. Size of labels indicate the ~~frequency~~ frequency of that keyword in the dataset while lines indicate co-occurrence links between keywords. In order to improve ~~the~~ legibility, only the strongest 1000 links have been mapped. Colors correspond to clusters described in section 3.2.

#INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE

#INSERT FIGURE 2 HERE

Keyword maps show the stability and predominance of wastewater treatment keywords, together with energy recovery related terminology and biological phenomena (such as bioremediation, biodegradation) related with soil and contamination management. The spatial positioning of items is roughly coherent with the clusters detected, with significant overlap in clusters where some transversality can be expected, such as clusters dealing with contaminants equally present in soil or water (heavy metals) or clusters related with general waste management.

The evolution of research topics from 2002 to 2012 can be explored by looking at the keywords that experience a sharp increase in occurrences in that interval. New and relevant terms (not existing in 2002 and in top 300 keywords in 2012) are Biochar, Closed-loop supply chains, Biohydrogen, Glycerol and Biorefinery. 4 out of 5 terms are closely related with energy generation practices.

Relevant terms that significantly increase their presence in 2012 (terms in the top 300 positions in 2012 that increase their share in the dataset by a factor higher than 7) are presented in table 3.

#INSERT TABLE 3 HERE

New techniques and materials related with wastewater treatment, soil amendment and energy generation present the sharpest increase, ~~not showing predominance regardless of any~~ research area.

3.2. CLUSTER ANALYSIS

As explained in section 2.3, the number of clusters to be obtained has been established by seeking equilibrium between the necessary data reduction for the interpretation and the minimization of ICD. Taking the inclusiveness of the definition chosen for WR into account, the prospect was finding a fairly high number of clusters reflecting research specialties in WR, each tackling a particular problem focused in a particular waste material or recycling technique. ~~The lines in Figure 31 lines~~ shows ICD decreasing with the increase in cluster number, ~~while~~ ~~vertical bars reflect the relative proportion of decrease in ICD.~~ Good “cutting” points for clusterization are those with a steep reduction in ICD distance, ~~whereas~~ a reduction of the data to 30-50 clusters is desirable.

~~#INSERT FIGURE 31 HERE~~

The flattening of the 2002 curve after 45 clusters indicates a good cutting point, ~~especially looking at considering the low reductions achieved in the next subsequent - intervals. while~~ ~~the~~ 2012 curve offers more opportunities in 20, 40 and 50 clusters, ~~but however~~ ~~it~~ in order to ease the comparison between 2002 and 2012, the cutting point has been defined ~~in~~ ~~at~~ 40 clusters for year 2012 data.

The WR research specialties revealed by cluster analysis are shown in table 4 and table 5. The grey cell indicates a cluster with no clear interpretation. This cluster has been labeled using its most frequently occurring keyword.

~~#INSERT TABLE 4 HERE~~

~~#INSERT TABLE 5 HERE~~

The cluster solutions for years 2002 and 2012 are similar in structure. A bird’s eye view of the identified clusters quickly indicates the mainstream of the overall WR researching activity: Water recovery, waste management, soil decontamination and amendment and energy sources, ~~as previously noticed in keyword map analysis~~. Very similar clusters to those in 2002 can be found in 2012, having some differences in their keyword composition, with the substitution of some techniques and resources for others, but generally addressing the same research problem. This is the case ~~of with clusters~~ “biomass combustion energy”, “wastewater treatment” and the related clusters (“nitrification/denitrification”, “oxidation techniques”) and “heavy metals” ~~clusters~~, among others. ~~It We~~ could ~~be said~~ say that the permanence of these clusters from year 2002 ~~display indicates~~ the backbone of WR research as defined in this study. Some clusters show a split, as is the case with “adsorption kinetics” or “cellulosic residues - ethanolization”, while others, ~~merge, like such as~~ “biodegradation techniques” and “bioremediation” ~~merge~~.

~~Cluster relationship study in next section will show that these are tightly related clusters, so this kind of evolution is something to be expected.~~

Nevertheless, some new clusters ~~can be~~ detected in 2012 ~~that~~ do not represent a completely new research area by themselves, but rather mark the consolidation of new research lines in areas already present in 2002. These are the “lignocellulosic bioethanol”, “algaculture and CO₂ fixation” and “biodiesel” clusters, closely related with the energy generation area, and the “inverse logistics & circular economy” cluster in the waste management area. Full details of the keyword contents of each cluster are available upon request to corresponding author.

The robustness of the clustering has been estimated by checking the similarity between the results obtained by hierarchical clustering and the clustering method available in VOSviewer. VOSviewer algorithm relies on modularity-based clustering (Waltman, Van Eck, & Noyons, 2010), an alternative to hierarchical methods, so the resemblance of the solutions obtained by such different approaches would indicate that some robustness can be expected from this analysis. Meila’s VI (2007) technique, as available in fpc R package (Hennig, 2013), has been used to quantify the normalized similarity between both approaches, resulting in 84.5% of similarity for year 2002 clustering and 78.8% for year 2012. Considering the methodological differences between hierarchical analysis and modularity-based clustering, it can be concluded that the clustering presented in this paper is reasonably robust.

[3.3.] MAPPING OF CLUSTERS DENSITY MAPS

The relationships between clusters ~~have~~ been explored using the density view available in VOSviewer. This visualization is particularly useful to ~~get~~obtain an overview of the general structure of a map and to draw attention to the most important areas in a map (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010). The following visualizations have been generated by shrinking the keyword map, grouping all keywords under the cluster to which they have been assigned ~~to~~ in hierarchical analysis. The similarity links between clusters have been calculated by ~~summing~~ adding up the keyword-keyword similarities that ~~tie~~ link them. Colors in these maps indicate the relative importance of each cluster as given by the sum of all the occurrences of keywords forming that cluster, from red to green, in a decreasing order of importance. In order to improve the pictures, overlapping of labels has been avoided by eliminating the less important labels. VOSviewer allows zooming into density maps to detect the lesser items. ~~rd~~Data files for building the maps are available upon request to the authors.

#INSERT FIGURE 4 HERE

#INSERT FIGURE 5 HERE

An important conglomerate of topics takes place in both years, formed by wastewater treatment and environmental remediation techniques, positioned on left side in 2002 map and on the upper right side of 2012 map. Wastewater techniques include wetlands, oxidation and filtration, with minor clusters related with particular effluents (textile effluents) or special recovery treatments in the surrounding of the dominant nucleus. Bioremediation and biodegradation form the mainstream of ~~the~~ environmental remediation area.

Bacterial-related clusters are also positioned in this zone for both years, indicating the wide use of microorganisms in pollution removal in water and soil. Wastewater and environmental remediation clusters show a significant overlap in both years, ~~pointing out indicating the applications~~ of bioremediation techniques ~~for recovering both to the recovery of~~ aquifers and soils.

Another common trait of both maps is the presence of the area formed by composting and manure/soil amendment clusters, ~~that~~ which remains stable and well defined over the time period studied, not surprisingly, some compost types are well-known soil amenders. Adsorption treatments and clusters related with heavy metals are also persistent, though losing some relevance. These are the areas with minor changes in scientific production from 2002 to 2012, according to our analysis.

Focusing on ~~notorious~~ notable changes, attention can be drawn to the following ~~evolutions/developments can be pointed out:~~

- 2002 map shows a concentration of clusters related to anaerobic treatments on the upper side of the map, showing a coherent grouping of related clusters that ~~appreciably sensibly~~ reduces its relevance in 2012, with some of the clusters disappearing from the map.
- Clusters ~~about~~ concerning management techniques show an interesting evolution, with the emergence of new research activities in 2012 ~~likesuch as~~ inverse logistics, a managerial concept that ~~involves taking into account~~ considers factors like the obsolescence of the product and its final disposal in the early stages of product design (Ramani, Ramanujan, Bernstein, Zhao, Sutherland, Handwerker, Choi, Kim, & Thurston, 2010), or product life cycle practices. All these areas are coherently grouped on the left side of 2012 map.
- Probably, the most ~~notorious~~ notable change can be attributed to energy-related clusters, as anticipated by keyword analysis in section 3.1. As ~~many uch~~ as six relevant clusters are directly related with energy recovery from waste sources in 2012 (see table 5) and the algorithm positioned them coherently packed on the lower part of the map.

— following a method successfully employed to characterize the main topics in news after terrorist attacks on 9/11, by analyzing the main keywords in press releases (Batagelj & Mrvar, 2001). Figure 2 shows the results of the first partitioning of year-2002 network by islands that put strongly connected clusters together. The node size reflects the size of the clusters, given by the occurrence frequency of the terms they contain. In other words, clusters containing very frequent terms appear in the form of bigger nodes on the map. Different islands are identified by colors, so clusters that have the same color become strongly related clusters that define a wider research area, often related with the recovery of a particular resource. Width and darkness of the lines indicate the strength of the relationship between clusters.

#INSERT FIGURE 2 HERE

Some relationships that could intuitively be deduced from cluster interpretation are confirmed by the island partitioning method. Figure 2 shows that agricultural waste-related clusters are strongly linked to energy production clusters, revealing a coherent

research area focused on extracting energy from cellulosic agricultural wastes. On the left of the map, soil amendment and heavy metals form an island, with chromium removal having sufficient importance to be differentiated from general heavy metal clusters. This cluster is particularly interesting because chromium removal terms appear associated to microorganisms, hence the “bioremediation” extension in this cluster name. Bioremediation is logically linked to bioaugmentation and biodegradation clusters, the presence of a composting cluster in this island indicates the presence, in year 2002 of research into the possibilities of compost as a bioremediator. Wastewater treatment and its related specialties form a logical and well defined island, as well as studies around anaerobic techniques. The relationship between manure and its uses and nitrification-denitrification treatments is pointed out by the data.

The biggest island detected in the first partitioning had comparatively weak links when compared with the rest, so it was excluded from the mapping in figure 2, and the island partitioning technique was repeated with its clusters. Figure 3 shows the results.

#INSERT FIGURE 3 HERE

These islands are based on weaker relationships than the previous ones, and some of the islands revealed in this second partitioning may be less logical. The analyst should conclude that some of the clusters reflect isolated research problems that show no clear links with others. Looking at figure 3, an area clearly focused on waste management can be detected, as well as an island containing clusters explicitly dealing with material recycling (building and plastic materials) and another tackling waste incineration issues. Three clusters related with microorganisms form an isolated research area. The interpretation of the rest of islands remains unclear.

The same method has been used with the network corresponding to year 2012, obtaining the maps shown in figures 4 and 5.

#INSERT FIGURE 4 HERE

Figure 4 shows changes in energy generation research, unveiling a triad of energy-related groupings that divide energy generation research lines in three areas: One of them is related with biomass energy, relating this cluster to agricultural residues. The second shows cellulose as an energy resource, with ethanolization playing a relevant role. The third area contains a cluster appearing in 2012 for the first time, related with the research of algae. It was not possible to infer the recycling purpose of algae research from the composition of this cluster, so a generic “algaculture & CO₂ fixation” was chosen to name it. Despite this, the island partitioning identifies a close relationship between algaculture and biodiesel, so this may be one of the main applications of algae in waste recycling.

Data in 2012 again show evidence of a tight relationship between bioremediation-biodegradation techniques, but in this case composting activities have been related to soil amendment and manure research, instead of being related to the bioremediation branch. The wastewater treatment area continues to keep the wastewater treatment cluster together with oxidation and physical separation (filtration, membranes) techniques, showing that research in these two clusters is strongly related to treatment of polluted water.

The heavy metal area noticeably changes in composition, as 2012 map includes adsorption and biochemical kinetics clusters, formerly part of wastewater treatment. The implications of this change in heavy metal removal research could be the subject of future studies. Permanence of this area throughout time confirms the relevance of heavy metals as a contaminant, and the research around their removal from various resources.

The biggest island resulting from this step again contained a subset of clusters with weaker relationships, so it was taken apart and the island partitioning method was run again using these clusters, resulting in the visualization of figure 5.

#INSERT FIGURE 5 HERE

General waste management research is split in two agglomerates, one related to municipal waste management and incineration, the other linking general waste management with research around inverse logistics & circular economy, a managerial concept that involves taking into account factors like the obsolescence of the product and its final disposal in the early stages of product design (Ramani, Ramanujan, Bernstein, Zhao, Sutherland, Handwerker, Choi, Kim, & Thurston, 2010). Properties of recycled materials again form an area in the 2012 second partitioning. Many wastewater related clusters together form a big island with some clusters of difficult interpretation in the wastewater framework, this may be indicative of isolation of these topics over time.

[4.] CONCLUSIONS

Depending on the source, available definitions vary considerably vary o in what can be considered WR science. This paper adopts an inclusive, wide-scope definition of WR and captures the research taking place being done in this science from properly selected databases. After eliminating abundant duplicities, a dataset containing PR journal articles published in years 2002 and 2012 has been built, and the information contained in the author keyword field has been analyzed combining text mining for data-cleaning, cluster analysis and network analysis advanced visualization tools. The results of the cluster analysis reveal the main research problems in WR being tackled by the scientific community, while the subsequent mapping and network analysis shows the overall structure of this field, by grouping closely related clusters in islands.

The results show that the data retrieval stage could be satisfactorily conducted in this case by exploiting the highest coverage database (SCOPUS) losing only roughly 8% of the information. A bird's eye view analysis of top keywords for years 2002 and 2012 reveals a fairly stable core research in WR pivoting around water and soil as resources to be recycled on one hand, and energy generation from waste resources on the other. Main emerging terms and new terms in 2012 do not show any departure from this overall structure, however, but a significant increase in research about concerning energy generation and waste management is detected.

A cluster analysis has been conducted using keyword co-occurrence data to set the similarities among keywords by calculating Salton's Cosine. Interpretation of the resulting clusters has been conducted done in close collaboration with experts in the field. The results show a set of fairly stable clusters that either remain very similar or slightly vary by scission or merging in the studied interval. These clusters represent various techniques of wastewater treatment, soil

remediation and amendment, and energy generation (particularly via agricultural wastes) that reflect the backbone of WR research. Main changes are given by a set of clearly defined energy generation and waste management clusters that emerge in 2012. The multiplication of research fronts sharing a common scientific area (energy generation from waste sources in this case) indicates maturity of the area, according to some authors (Moya-Anegón, 2010). The robustness of the clustering has been tested by comparing the results against the clustering proposed by VOSviewer software, following the method developed by Meila (2007). A similarity of 84.5% for year 2002 clustering and 78.8% for year 2012 is deemed to be enough sufficient to confirm the robustness of the results presented in this study, taking into account the differences between hierarchical clustering versus modularity based clustering method (VOSviewer).

The VOSviewer visualization tool has been used to build keyword maps reflecting both the similarity-based spatial positioning of VOSviewer and the results from clustering analysis, by item colors. Both criteria are found to be significantly coincident. Not surprisingly, a strong overlap is detected between the keywords of related clusters and between the peripheral keywords of some unrelated clusters. Density maps come to provide a clearer reading of the scientific structure of the WR field.

The last step of the analysis builds density maps with the aim of defining wider research areas formed by sets of related clusters. This step takes the characterization of WR a step further, identifying a big large area of research that remains fairly stable in the time interval studied, pivoting around the recovery of basic, widely used raw materials such as like water and fertile soil. Heavy metals as attention-catching prominent contaminants, and microorganisms as pollution removal tools go together in this area. Other research problems that maintain their overall structure and relationship throughover time are compost and manure & soil amendment clusters. Adsorption research also plays a relevant role in both years under study. used network analysis tools

The most notorious notable evolution in WR research from 2002 to 2012 corresponds to the growth, both in relevance and diversification, of energy recovery and waste management areas. Both cluster analysis and keyword analysis come to illustrate this fact, and density visualization clearly packs together related clusters together, confirming the internal coherence of these research areas. New clusters emerge that reflect new research problems and ideas being addressed by the scientific community, setting a starting point for further research in these areas. This being an analysis restricted to the top 300 keywords of each year, emergence and growth of new clusters must has to be done at the expense of others, and the widebroad research area around anaerobiosis in 2002 map is sensibly appreciably reduced in 2012. The reasons behind the lessening in the waning attention paid to this research area could again be the subject object of study in future work.

4. FUTURE LINES OF RESEARCH

to reveal relationships between the clusters. If clusters reflect research problems or specialties being addressed, then the islands detected in this stage define wider research areas formed by sets of related clusters. This step added detail to the areas previously deduced from cluster interpretation, and revealed more clues about the evolution of research. Main changes in

areas correspond to reallocations of clusters from one research area to another. Most of these reallocated clusters represent research fronts dealing with techniques (adsorption) or physical parameters (kinetics) that are not constrained to the recovery of a particular raw material. Further research can be conducted to delve deeper into the reasons behind these reallocations, but this is beyond the scope of this paper.

The energy generation area shows a completely different evolution. It appears that research into extracting energy from waste sources has significantly evolved since year 2002, with the emergence of new clusters that reflect new research problems which, at the same time, form a set of three well-differentiated research areas that seem to be quite focused on a particular technique oriented at the objection of energy from a particular source. Once again, this is a conclusion that could be expanded and improved by further research.

Analysis of secondary partitions reveals two areas present in both 2002 and 2012. One of them deals with recycled material properties, while the other contains clusters related with management research. The study of material properties remains unchanged in 2012, but management research is split in two parts differencing between municipal waste management and an area containing the new cluster "inverse logistics & circular economy". The differences between management of industrial and municipal wastes may be the trigger behind this split.

This paper took a broad, diverse terrain to overview the use of using bibliometric tools. Main landforms, rivers and villages have been recognized and identified, setting a necessary cornerstone for guiding further research in WR characterization. The main areas where significant changes are occurring have been identified and characterized, forming a useful basemap for future works focusing on the dynamics of change of WR scientific fields.

In addition to this, WR mapping could be extended to other data sources, including items other than PR journal articles, likesuch as -conference proceedings and trade and professional journals. The authors are particularly interested in adapting the query system to be run on patent databases in order ; to obtain a technology map of the WR field and conduct further research on the science-technology transferences that may be taking place within this field.

and further research is already underway to explore some of the highlighted areas in greater detail. Let this work be a starting point for further endeavors into WR science characterization.

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Fig.2 Keyword map for year 2012.

Fig. 31 Variation of ICD with cluster number, for years 2002 and 2012

Table 4 Cluster structure of WR research in year 2002

Wastewater treatment – techniques	Anaerobiosis	Nutrients	Recyclable plastic materials – properties	Bioaugmentation
Biodegradation techniques	Adsorption kinetics	Persistent organic elements toxicity	Heavy metals – Zn, Cr, Cd	Biofilms
Biomass combustion energy	Mathematic tools	Filtration-membranes	Biologic energy sources	Plastic materials, properties and decomposition
Sludge and soil Amendment	Incineration wastes	Phenolics treatment	VOC management and analytics	UASB reactors
Heavy metals contamination	Waste management	Waste incineration	Agricultural waste	Anaerobic gases
Bioremediation	Agricultural residue energy	Cellulosic residues - ethanolization	Enzymatic degradation of agricultural waste	Catalytic phenomena and catalyzers
Composting	Activated carbon	Microorganisms & fungi	Sustainable development studies	Proteins
Municipal waste landfilling	Nitrification - denitrification	Bacterial cultures & growth	Chromium removal - bioremediation	Recycled building materials
Manure and soil amendment	Decontamination by immobilization using enzyme & cells	Wastewater treatment - wetlands	Oxidation techniques	Biochemical reduction techniques.

Table 5 Cluster structure of WR research in year 2012

Biomass combustion energy	Advanced agricultural waste management	Biochemical kinetics	Recyclable materials properties	Textile industry contaminants
Soil remediation	Anaerobiosis	Composting	Algaculture and CO2 fixation	Heavy metals –Zn, Cu, Cd, Pb
Wastewater treatment	Life cycle analysis & bioenergy in climatic change studies.	Catalysis and catalyzers for hydrogen generation	Filtration – membranes	Inverse logistics and circular economy
Agricultural residue energy	Adsorption	Municipal waste	Nitrification – denitrification	Analytic tools

		landfilling		
Biodegradation – bioremediation	Heavy metal treatment	Waste incineration – WEEE	Cellulose as a resource	Phenolics treatment
Manure and soil amendment	Fly ash management	Oxidation techniques	Activated sludge techniques optimization	Nutrients
Lignocellulosic bioethanol	Mathematic tools	Wastewater treatment - wetlands	Materials from recycled concrete	Coagulation – flocculation
Edaphic bacterial ecology	Waste management	Compost & manure gaseous emissions	Biodiesel	Photocatalysis

Fig. 4 Density map corresponding to 2002 clusters.

Fig. 3 Second partitioning of year 2002 network, analyzing the less cohesive island

Fig. 4 First partitioning of year 2012 network. Links weaker than 0.15 have been removed from the original keyword network

Fig. 5 Second partitioning of year 2012 network, analyzing the less cohesive island